

REVOLUTIONIZING THE WORLD OF SOCIAL IMPACT BONDS: THE BUSINESS CASE FOR DLTS AND BLOCKCHAIN EXPERIMENTS

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Abstract - As blockchain and DLTS technology makes its presence felt strongly in many industries like finance and banking, this study investigates the business case for the application to social impact bonds (SIBs). Technological innovation in general, and distributed ledger technology (DLT) in particular, could become a game changer in the development of new social impact bonds sector. This paper discusses the potential impact of DLT on SIBs market and the potential scenarios of DLT adoption. Alongside presenting a strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats analysis (SWOT), the study exhibits the requirements for and steps toward a SIBs structure facilitated by blockchain technology.

Keywords - Social Impact Bonds, Swot Analysis, Blockchain and DLTS Technology
